

Primary healthcare providers

Gary Schlesinger is [the founder and CEO at Parcare](#), a major primary care provider, shares that primary healthcare providers play an indispensable role in the healthcare system to prevent and manage common health conditions. They can lead patients to make healthy decisions and recommend treatment depending on the symptoms of the diseases they present. Its role is particularly important in the early stages of the disease.

Gary Schlesinger indicates that primary care can be explained as the scope of complete first medical contact and ongoing care for a patient whose symptoms, health problems or signs have not been diagnosed, whatever the organ involved, the patient group, the origin of clinical delivery or diagnosis.

It involves a complete team of services for example:

- Health promotion
- Preventive health
- Advice
- Health education
- Diagnosis and treatment of diseases, is it acute or chronic

The advantages of primary care include its location in the patient's community, ensuring easy access, a personal physician, and also freeing up the availability of referral services to specialists in case of need.

[Gary Schlesinger](#) points out that there are several different types of primary healthcare providers that differ according to their educational background, experience and the services they can offer.

Here, Gary Schlesinger will share more about primary care physician.

Primary Care Physician

Gary Schlesinger shares that [the primary care physician](#) is the point of first entry for much of the general population. These doctors are often the people who create the seat in the healthcare system for any medical issues that may arise. In addition, they are responsible for coordinating the total healthcare of their patients. They are generally family medicine, internal medicine or pediatric doctors. Additionally, many women choose an obstetrician or gynecologist as their primary care doctor.

Primary care physicians play many important roles in improving health outcomes. These can include:

- Encouraging patients to take preventive measures for their health (e.g. quitting smoking, exercising regularly, eating a healthy diet)
- Promote health initiatives to improve patient health
- Screening patients for early signs of chronic diseases, such as heart disease and cancers
- Educating patients about their health and offering relevant information about diseases and treatments
- Counseling patients on their health and giving appropriate advice when applicable

- Diagnosing and treating diseases based on current symptoms and relevant guidelines

Each physician has a unique style in the way they offer healthcare to their patients. For this reason, it is important for each individual to find a doctor that they know and can trust with decisions about their health.